

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS PART IV. CHROMIUM BISBIGUANIDINES.

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The present paper deals with the preparation, properties and the constitution of chromium bis-biguanidines. The free hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide has been prepared and found to behave as diacidic base in aqueous solution.

In the previous communications (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670; Rây and Ghosh, *this issue*, p.) the preparation, properties and the constitution of chromium tris-biguanidines and chromium tris-phenylbiguanidines have been reported upon. It was already mentioned (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*) that the chromium tris-biguanide base and its salts undergo, on keeping in dilute aqueous solution, gradual hydrolysis with elimination of a biguanide molecule, giving rise to a new series of bis-biguanidine complexes, as represented below :

where BigH = one biguanide molecule, X = OH, Cl, Br, etc. This corresponds to the tetrammines of the metalammine complexes, just as the tris-biguanidines represent the hexammines. The bis-biguanidine complexes form bivalent cations in keeping with the character of tris-biguanidines which form trivalent ones. That the formation of complex biguanide bases and salts is due to secondary co-ordination by the free amino-group of the primary metal-biguanide complex is hereby well illustrated.

The chromium bis-biguanidines again, in dilute aqueous solution, undergo further hydrolysis on keeping and form complex monobiguanidine products with elimination of a second biguanide molecule. The latter hydrolyse further leading finally to chromium hydroxide.

It has not yet been possible to prepare this monobiguanide complex in a pure state.

The constitution of the hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide compounds can be represented by the following figure.

The hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide hydrochloride, when kept for a long time over concentrated H_2SO_4 , or heated to $120^\circ-130^\circ$, loses water even from the complex zone, giving rise to a product of the composition $Cr(BigH^+)_2 \cdot OH \cdot X_2$, but no di-ol binuclear compound of the type

as might be expected. For, the anhydro-compound on keeping in air regains rapidly the whole of its original water-content, regenerating the parent hydroxo-aquo-compound. Further-more, the solution of the anhydro-compound is slightly alkaline and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts like the original hydroxo-aquo-compound. A di-ol compound, as is well-known, is neutral and does not liberate ammonia from ammonium salts. This hydroxo-aquo-compound evidently possesses a *cis*-configuration, being produced by the elimination of one bidentate biguanide radicle from the complex zone, which occupied *cis*-positions in the same. This is confirmed by the fact that the complex hydroxo-aquo-compound readily reacts with ethylenediamine giving rise to mixed amines. That this *cis*-hydroxo-aquo-compound does not give rise to a di-ol complex on dehydration is due to the greater tendency of the Cl-ion from the outer zone to co-ordinate with the central Cr atom than that of the two complex residues to condense with elimination of water.

A chlorine ion becomes bound by co-ordination with Cr atom and the complex becomes a univalent cation by this internal compensation. In aqueous solution, however, it rapidly reverts at the ordinary temperature to the original hydroxo aquo type; freezing-point measurement, on the other hand, indicates its existence at low temperature.

A solution of the hydrochloride, which, as its conductivity shows, dissociates into two ions besides the complex ion, on keeping for a day or

two fails to precipitate silver chloride on addition of silver nitrate. The solution becomes only slightly opalescent; but the whole of the silver chloride is precipitated by the addition of a neutral salt like NH_4NO_3 . How can an aged solution of a crystalline complex salt prevent the formation or growth of silver chloride particles is difficult to account for! The same strange property, as already stated (vide Part I), is also exhibited by the complex *tris*-biguanide hydrochloride and hydrobromide. The *bis*-biguanide hydrobromide, and to a less extent the hydriodide, also behave similarly. Even a fresh solution of the hydrochloride shows a tendency towards such behaviour.

The free hydroxo-aquo-chromium *bis*-biguanide base has been prepared from the sulphate by decomposition with baryta, which, in aqueous solution, behaves as a diacidic base and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium-bis-biguanide Sulphate.—A concentrated solution of chromium *tris*-biguanide hydroxide (7 g.) was treated with a concentrated solution of ammonium sulphate. The sparingly soluble complex *tris*-biguanide sulphate was precipitated with liberation of ammonia. On warming on the water-bath, the latter went into solution in ammonia and, at the same time, gradually hydrolysed into the very sparingly soluble hydroxo-aquo-chromium *bis*-biguanide sulphate, which separated as a violet-coloured crystalline precipitate. This was washed first with hot water and then with alcohol. The product was dried in air. Yield 4 g.

On treatment with warm NaOH solution the substance is converted into chromium *tris*-biguanide hydroxide which separates as ruby-red crystals. The sulphate does not lose any water even when heated to 120° . {Found: N, 36.14, 36.2; S, 8.16, 8.17; Cr, 13.50, 13.70. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{-OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4$ requires N, 36.35; S, 8.30; Cr, 13.50 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-Biguanide Hydrochloride.—It was prepared by digesting the above-described hydroxo-aquo-sulphate in slight excess with the solution of a calculated quantity of barium chloride. The mixture was gently warmed on the water-bath and filtered. The filtrate was treated with a few c.c. of a concentrated solution of ammonium chloride and a little alcohol, and then allowed to stand overnight. The rose-red crystals that separated were filtered, washed at first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. They were afterwards dried in air. The mother-liquor, on keeping, gave a second crop of the hydrochloride.

The same compound was also formed when a concentrated solution of the chromium *tris*-biguanide base was heated on the water-bath with ammonium chloride. The solution, on keeping, deposited crystals of the hydrochloride.

The substance is readily soluble in water. The solution is slightly alkaline to litmus and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts. On treatment with warm caustic alkali solution, the chromium *tris*-biguanide base is formed. Acids lead to decomposition and formation of chromic salts. Freshly prepared concentrated solution gave an immediate precipitate with a solution of silver or thallos nitrate. But from an aged solution (after 24 hours) silver nitrate failed to precipitate AgCl, and gave only a slight turbidity. Addition of an electrolyte like NH_4NO_3 produced, however, an immediate and complete precipitation. On keeping the aged solution mixed with silver nitrate, the colour became darker and a grey precipitate of a mixture of metallic silver and AgCl separated on boiling with ammonium nitrate solution. Metallic silver probably resulted from the reduction of a little Ag_2O , formed by the alkaline reaction of the hydroxo-salt. {Found : N, 36'67, 36'9 ; Cl, 18'70, 18'74 ; Cr, 13'90, 13'85. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3 \cdot \text{OH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 36'50 ; Cl, 18'78 ; Cr, 13'76 per cent}.

An anhydrous variety $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3 \cdot \text{OH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{Cl}_2$ was obtained in winter season. Keeping over concentrated H_2SO_4 till the weight became constant, the hydrated variety was found to lose 10'2% by weight, which corresponds to a loss of two molecules of water. {Found : N, 41'20 ; Cl, 20'65. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3 \cdot \text{OH} \cdot \text{Cl}] \text{Cl}$ requires N, 41'20 ; Cl, 20'76 per cent}.

This anhydrous compound readily regained its original weight on keeping in air. Determination of the molecular weight by the freezing-point method indicates the existence of this chloro-hydroxo-salt in aqueous solution at a low temperature (*vide infra*). With rise of temperature, however, it changes into the hydroxo-aquo compound regenerating the complex bivalent cation as the conductivity values show.

Equivalent conductivity at 28'3°.

ν ...	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048
λ_v ...	95'21	103'7	113'7	122'6	129'7	136'1	141'9

The acido-pentammine chromic salts, which also dissociate into two ions, besides the complex ion, show an equivalent conductivity of 140 mhos at 1000 ν at 25°, λ_v for $1/2 \text{BaCl}_2$ and λ_v for NH_4Cl at 1024 ν at 25° are also 135 and 147 respectively. The result, therefore, supports the constitution suggested for the complex.

Mol. wt. from the freezing-point.

Substance (anhydrous).	Depression Δ .	Mol. wt (found). m.	Vant Hoff's factor $i \sim M/m$.	Degree of dissociation $\alpha = (i-1)/n-1$.
0.32 g	0.03°	192	1.875	0.44

The dissociation is rather abnormally weak at 0°. This seems to suggest that at low temperature the hydroxo-aquo salt changes into the chloro-hydroxo variety representing the solid anhydrous compound and dissociates into two ions. In that case $\alpha = 0.875$.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide bromide was obtained as a rose-red crystalline precipitate from a solution of the chloride by the addition of a concentrated solution of NH_4Br in the cold, washed and dried as in the previous case. {Found : Br, 35.20 ; Cr, 11.69. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{Br}_2$ requires Br, 35.41 ; Cr, 11.58 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide hydriodide was prepared like the hydrobromide from a solution of the hydrochloride by the addition of NH_4I . It is a rose-coloured crystalline substance soluble in water. {Found : I, 46.0 ; Cr, 9.76. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{I}_2$ requires I, 46.79 ; Cr, 9.57 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide nitrate was prepared from the sulphate by digestion with the solution of a calculated amount of barium nitrate. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath, filtered and the filtrate cooled in ice, after adding a few c.c. of a concentrated solution of ammonium nitrate and a little alcohol. The violet-red crystals were washed and dried as previously described. {Found : N, 40.16 ; Cr, 12.68. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{NO}_3)_2$ requires N, 40.68, Cr, 12.60 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide thiosulphate was obtained as violet-red, sparingly soluble crystals by adding a solution of sodium thiosulphate to that of the complex hydrochloride. {Found : S, 15.84 ; Cr, 12.94. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ requires S, 15.96 ; Cr, 12.97 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide chromate was obtained as a dark buff, sparingly soluble, crystalline powder from potassium chromate and the complex hydrochloride. {Found : Cr (total), 24.30 ; Cr (as CrO_4), 11.90. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{CrO}_4\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cr (total), 24.59, Cr (as CrO_4), 12.29 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-Biguanide Camphorsulphonate.—It separated from the filtrate of the normal camphorsulphonate (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*) as a rose-red crystalline deposit. {Found : N, 18.70 ; S, 8.70 ; Cr, 7.10. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}\cdot\text{SO}_3)_2$ requires N, 18.64 ; S, 8.52 ; Cr, 7.05 per cent}.

Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-biguanide hydroxide was prepared by digesting the sulphate with a solution of the calculated quantity of barium hydroxide. The mixture was gently warmed on the water-bath and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation *in vacuo* over concentrated H_2SO_4 deposited violet crystals, of which the large-sized ones were carefully picked up and washed several times by decantation with ice-cold water and finally with alcohol. The crystals were dried over a little solid KOH. {Found : N, 42.70; Cr, 16.22. $[Cr(BigH^+)_2 \cdot OH \cdot H_2O] (OH)_2$ requires N, 43.30; Cr, 16.10 per cent}.

The substance reacts strongly alkaline to litmus and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts. It did not give any precipitate of Ag_2O with silver nitrate solution, due probably to the formation of complex silver compound of a higher order; but on warming the solution, metallic silver was precipitated with formation of chromate. It lost three molecules of water with partial decomposition when heated to $105^\circ-110^\circ$.

A solution of the chloride gave crystalline precipitates with sodium dithionate (silky rose-red), sodium carbonate (rose-red), potassium ferrocyanide (pale rose) and also with potassium ferri- and cobaltcyanides.

Hydrolysis of Hydroxo-aquo-chromium bis-Biguanidines.—From the filtrate of the hydroxo-aquo-sulphate an insoluble ash-coloured substance separated on dilution and keeping. This was found to contain biguanide and sulphate besides chromium. An analysis of the product gave a ratio of chromium : biguanide : sulphate as 5 : 2 : 1.5.

Attempt was made to prepare the pure chloride from the insoluble sulphate by digesting the latter with the solution of a calculated quantity of $BaCl_2$. A dingy blue-violet filtrate was obtained which, on evaporation to dryness over concentrated H_2SO_4 gave a glassy mass. This on analysis gave a ratio of chromium : biguanide : chloride as 3 : 2 : 2.25 (approx.). The substance is slightly alkaline to litmus.

These are evidently mixtures of polyhydroxy compounds resulting from the gradual hydrolysis of the hydroxo-aquo-chromium *bis-biguanidines*. The final product of the hydrolysis is obviously chromium hydroxide.